

Registration of Thi Mai Anh Tran for Participation in BMF CP117 on Environmental Values and Information Quality

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Before joining the project “BMF CP117: Environmental Values Consideration, Information Quality, and Smart Home Energy Management System Adoption in the United States” on the SM3D Portal, I fully endorse the philosophy, principles, and ethical standards of the SM3D research community [1].

By joining this project, I commit to completing assigned tasks responsibly and within agreed timelines. I recognize that timely delivery supports coordination, accountability, and effective collaboration among project members. I will communicate clearly with collaborators and respond promptly to project-related requests.

I will maintain analytical rigor, theoretical clarity, and internal consistency throughout the research process. In line with the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework [2], I will ensure that

conceptual reasoning, empirical modeling, and interpretation align logically and remain theoretically defensible. When necessary, I will adopt methodological or analytical improvements that strengthen the robustness and explanatory value of the study, transparent research practices, including the responsible sharing of data, analytical code, and intermediate results, subject to ethical and project-specific constraints.

I will engage with all project members respectfully and professionally. I value diverse perspectives and will contribute to constructive discussion, provide thoughtful feedback, and respond openly to critique. I will support a collaborative research environment grounded in mutual respect and academic integrity.

Within my capacity and expertise, I am willing to contribute to the broader development of the SM3D community by promoting ethical research conduct, methodological rigor, and responsible knowledge sharing.

This statement reflects my commitment to collaborative scholarship, research integrity, and the successful completion of this project.

References

[1] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH (2025) Developing Bayesian probabilistic reasoning capacity in HSS disciplines: Qualitative evaluation on bayesvl and BMF analytics for ECRs. <https://dipot.ulb.ac.be/dspace/bitstream/2013/397326/3/wp25008.pdf>

[2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, La VP (2022) *The mindsponge and BMF analytics for innovative thinking in social sciences and humanities*. Berlin, Germany: De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.2478/9788367405119>

